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According to a study conducted by the Ministry of Health of Ukraine, cancer is the leading cause of death among all age groups of both sexes. The most common causes of death are malignant tumors of the breast, lungs, rectum and colon, prostate, skin and stomach. It is known that oncogenesis and tumor progression are closely linked to cell signaling pathways, which are normally aimed at cell proliferation and survival. The proteins that make up the PI3K/AKT/mTOR pathway can promote metastasis and the development of malignant tumors, making them a promising target for oncology research and targeted therapy. This article explores the role of the PAM signaling pathway in oncogenesis and the possibility of its use as a molecular basis for diagnosis and therapeutic targeting in patients with malignant tumors.

Keywords: PI3K/Akt/mTOR pathway, cancer, oncogenesis, targeted therapy.

Introduction

The PI3K/AKT/mTOR signaling pathway is a network of intracellular signaling in eukaryotic cells aimed at the proliferation and survival of newly formed cells. In addition, it is cross-talked with several other signaling pathways (MAPK, Ras, JAK-STAT). Consequently, dysregulation of signal transduction may contribute to the development of malignant tumors and resistance to anticancer therapy. According to sequencing data using a panel of 520 genes in women with stage I-III breast cancer, changes in the PI3K/AKT/mTOR signaling pathway were detected in 62.5% of patients. The most frequently altered genes were *PIK3CA* (45%), *PTEN* (7.5%), *AKT1* (5.9%), *PIK3R1* (2.7%) and *PIK3CG* (2%). According to the analysis of overall survival, it was significantly lower in patients with multiple PIK3 mutations [3, 13, 14]. In a study of head and neck cancer, significant associations were found between PI3K-AKT-mTOR mutations associated with the *PIK3CA* pathway and advanced TNM stage, as well as a correlation between the presence of *PIK3CA* mutations and HPV-associated oropharyngeal cancer [7]. Considering that excessive activation of the PAM pro-

notes metastasis through increased epithelial-mesenchymal transition and cell migration, late stage TNM in patients with aberrations of this signaling pathway will be associated with this [2, 4]. Mutations of the gene encoding the tumor suppressor PTEN are quite significant, and they are associated with the development of Cowden's syndrome (tumor hamartoma syndrome), which causes the development of both benign and malignant tumors of the breast, thyroid, endometrium, colon, kidneys and skin (melanoma).

In the diagnosis and prognosis of, for example, breast cancer treatment, immunohistochemistry is currently the most commonly used method based on criteria such as: Er, Pr, Her2, Ki-67, but PI3K-AKT-mTOR is also a potential prognostic factor and may become a molecular basis for future research on therapeutic targeting in patients with malignant tumors of the breast, thyroid, colorectal and oropharyngeal areas, and hematological diseases. In the clinical trials stage, there are non-specific and specific PI3K inhibitors, AKT inhibitors that demonstrate high anti-tumor activity against solid tumors and hematological neoplasms. There is a possibility of using these drugs in the monotherapy of hematological diseases (Copanlisib), in patients with

relapsed refractory chronic lymphocytic leukemia (Duvelisib), solid tumors and advanced breast tumors (Idelalisib).

We obtained data from PubMed, Molecular cancer, and Google academy on the association of mutations in the PAM signaling pathway and the development of malignant tumors with the possibility of improving the diagnosis and targeted therapy of cancer. All the manuscripts were published in 2017-2023. The literature review includes 500 scientific sources, of which 15 are included in the article. The focus is mainly on solid tumors of the breast, rectum and colon with the possibility of treatment with selective and non-selective PI3K and AKT inhibitors.

Functioning and Roles of the PAM Pathway

Multicellular organisms consist of an ordered and controlled population of cells. The functioning of such multicellular organisms depends not only on material and energy metabolism, but also on intercellular communication and signal regulation. The PAM pathway is a network of intracellular signals aimed at regulating many intracellular processes: survival, proliferation, growth, metabolism, and angiogenesis.

Signaling begins with the activation of receptors with tyrosine kinase activity by ligands (insulin, growth factors), followed by autophosphorylation of the receptor. Subsequently, SCH, GRB-2, and SOS proteins join the phosphorylated region of the receptor to form a complex which is capable of metabolizing guanine and, consequently, interacting with Ras proteins. Thus, Ras-GTP complexes are formed, which can engage in reactions of the MAPK or ROS pathway. In addition, the phosphorylated receptors can be joined by the IRS protein and components of phosphoinositide-3-kinase. PI3 kinase has a regulatory p85 and a catalytic p110 subunit that interact with the phosphorylated IRS protein, but in this condition PI3 is inactive. Activation of phosphoinositide-3-kinase occurs with the participation of Ras-GTP, followed by transformation of PIR1, 2 and PDK1, 2 proteins. After translocation of PDK1, 2 proteins into the cell cytoplasm, their interaction with serine/threonine protein kinase B becomes possible. PDK1 is phosphorylated at Thr308 in the catalytic region of AKT kinase, and PDK2 is phosphorylated at Ser473 in the regulatory region, which allows further regulation of cell growth and metabolism indirectly through phosphorylation of GSK-3, FoxOs, Bad, Caspase 9, nuclear transcription factor kappa B (NF-kappa B), mTOR and p21. mTOR, in turn, activates protein synthesis indirectly through CAD, resulting in increased nucleotide synthesis and directly affecting ribosomes and transcription initiation factors. At the same time, mTOR activation reduces apoptosis, autophagy and protein degradation by interacting with ULK1, TFEB, HIF and Erk5 proteins. Thus, aberration of the RAS signaling pathway can occur through induction of oncogenes upstream of PI3K, mutation or amplification of kinases such as PIK3CA, downregulation or inactivation of the tumor suppressor PTEN, and amplification and gain-of-function of missense mutations in the oncogene AKT [2].

Aberrations of the PAM Pathway

Aberrations of the PAM signaling pathway are one of the most prevalent in oncogenesis being detected in

50% of tumors. Dysfunction of the components of this pathway, such as PI3K hyperactivity, loss of PTEN function, and increased AKT function, are known factors of treatment resistance and disease progression in cancer (Fig. 1). The two main functional proteins of this pathway are PI3K and AKT [2]. Among them, one of the most frequent is the activating mutation or amplification of the *PIK3CA* gene encoding the catalytic subunit p110 α of PI3K, which is usually accompanied by the development of colorectal, breast, lung, gastric, and cervical cancers. In addition, in a mouse experiment, it was shown that PI3K mutation and loss of PTEN coexist in patients with prostate cancer and synergistically interact to accelerate carcinogenesis and tumor progression [12].

Therefore, PI3K is one of the main targets for the treatment of malignant tumors. Over the past decades, PI3K inhibitors have been registered and approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) [15].

PI3K inhibitors

It is important to note that PI3K inhibitors are classified into three main groups: pan-PI3K inhibitors (pan-PI3Ki), isoform PI3K inhibitors (IS PI3Ki) and dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitors (dual PI3K/mTOR) [15]. Clinical trials of pan-PI3Ki are still ongoing, but only copanlisib, a potent and selective inhibitor targeting PI3K isoforms p110 α and p110 δ , has achieved significant efficacy [5]. Copanlisib, a pan-PI3K inhibitor, is not only effective on its own, but also well combined with other antineoplastic drugs. It has been successfully implemented in combination with ibrutinib, gemcitabine, bendamustine, rituximab or rituximab + cyclophosphamide + doxorubicin + vincristine + prednisone in hematological tumors, and in combination with refametinib, gemcitabine or gemcitabine + cisplatin in solid tumors [10].

Inhibitors of PI3K isoforms demonstrate a broader therapeutic index and less toxic effects on non-target cells due to reduced expression of various PI3K isoforms in non-cancerous cells. Particularly, high antitumor activity has been demonstrated in the monotherapy of breast cancer and other common solid tumors [8].

The group of dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitors (PI3K/mTORi) has a broad spectrum of action, inhibiting all PI3K isoforms as well as mTORC1/mTORC2. This leads to the blocking of three important PAM signaling pathways, making them prospective antineoplastic drugs. Clinical trials are currently being conducted to evaluate the efficacy of apitolizib, dactolizib, paxalizib (monotherapy for advanced solid tumors), gedatolizib and samotolizib (monotherapy/combination for advanced solid tumors), and voxalozib (monotherapy/combination for hematological malignancies and advanced solid tumors).

AKT Inhibitors

Mutations of the *AKT* gene are much less frequent in human malignancies. Nevertheless, AKT, a signaling pathway that promotes cancer growth, is overactivated in a subset of precancerous breast lesions. This hyperactivity is observed in 33% of ductal carcinoma in situ and 38% of invasive breast cancer cases. It is important to note that most of these tumors (79%) also

have estrogen receptors [11]. In addition, clinical trials are currently underway for such drugs as capivasertib, ipatasertib and M2698. Among them, capivasertib is the most effective inhibitor of all three forms of AKT and is the drug of choice, especially in breast cancer [9].

Challenges and Adverse Effects

The study and investigation of targets of the PAM signaling pathway provides opportunities for improved diagnosis and personalized treatment of cancer, particularly for resistant and recurrent tumors. Although some PI3K and AKT inhibitors have been approved by the FDA, there are still concerns about the development of resistance, susceptibility markers and toxicology. For example, for copanlisib, treatment-related adverse events of any degree include hyperglycemia, leukopenia, diarrhea, hypertension, neutropenia, nausea, thrombocytopenia and infections. Serious side effects include pneumonia (8%), pneumonitis (5%) and hyperglycemia (5%) [6]. When selective PI3K inhibitors are used in patients with CLL/AML, immune-related toxicities of grade ≥ 3 include colitis (12%), pneumonitis (3%), elevated alanine aminotransferase (ALT) (3%) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) (3%); in addi-

tion, pneumonia (15%) is the most reported serious adverse event [1]. Despite several adverse effects, however, these drugs are better tolerated by patients than traditional chemotherapy.

Conclusions

1. Research on the PI3K/AKT/mTOR signaling pathway and its role in oncogenesis is actively ongoing, and mutations are detected in a wide variety of malignancies: colorectal cancer, breast cancer, lung, gastric, cervical, CLL and AML.

2. New data on this signaling pathway may provide the basis for the elaboration of new and more effective cancer treatments.

3. Several groups of PI3K, AKT and mTOR inhibitors have been developed and demonstrated effectiveness in the treatment of various types of cancer.

4. PI3K/AKT/mTOR inhibitors can be used as monotherapy or in combination with other anticancer drugs.

5. Targeted therapy of the PI3K/AKT/mTOR signaling pathway has several significant advantages over conventional chemotherapy, such as lower toxicity and better tolerability.

Tables and Figures

Fig. 1 Mechanism of the PI3K/Akt/mTOR signaling pathway and targets of drugs for targeted therapy (created using the Canva tool)

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